

Deliverable 2.1.1.1

LIST AND GRAPHIC OVERVIEW ON RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS

05.11.2024

D2.1.1.1 List and graphic overview on relevant stakeholders

Nina Kerker (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1584-3089>)¹, Christina Speck (<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7386-8334>)², Franziska M. Hoffart (<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4719-9147>)^{1,3,5}, Zhiyu Pan (<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4949-2782>)⁴

¹ Sociological Research Institute Göttingen e.V., <https://sofi.uni-goettingen.de/>, Friedländer Weg 31, 37085 Göttingen

² Karlsruhe Institute of Technology, Kaiserstraße 89, 76133 Karlsruhe

³ Department of Energy, Transportation, Environment, German Institute for Economic Research (DIW Berlin), Berlin, Germany

⁴ RWTH Aachen University, Mathieustraße 10, 52074 Aachen

⁵ Kassel Institute for Sustainability, University of Kassel, Germany

Published by

Sociological Research Institute Göttingen (SOFI) e.V., Germany

Acknowledgements

The authors of this article have used various preparatory works from the NFDI4Energy to create this portrait, and references have been made where possible. Thanks to all those who are not named.

The authors would like to thank the German Federal Government, the German State Governments, and the Joint Science Conference (GWK) for their funding and support as part of the NFDI4Energy consortium. The work was funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG) – 501865131 within the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI, www.nfdi.de).

License

This document is published under the Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0). This license allows users to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the material in any medium or format, so long as attribution is given to the creator.

The license allows for commercial use.

Table of Contents

General Information.....	3
Summary	3
Deliverable within NFDI4Energy.....	4
Deliverable.....	5
1. List of central stakeholder groups	5
2. Graphical stakeholder overview	10
3. Potential stakeholder involvement.....	11
References.....	12

General Information

Summary

This deliverable aims to identify all relevant stakeholders for whom the NFDI4Energy platform and its outputs might be interesting and useful. We differentiate between three major stakeholder groups: the energy research community, industry partners and societal stakeholders. As a result of our explorative analytical considerations, possible inputs (i.e., research artefacts that can be contributed by the stakeholder group) and possible outputs (i.e., research artefacts that are required by the stakeholder group) were collected by the authors of this deliverable. Moreover, potential barriers of platform usage and artifact sharing have been outlined.

Since the NFDI4Energy project considers the needs and interests of these three stakeholder groups across multiple Task Areas (primarily within Task Area 1 to Task Area 3), the information on each stakeholder group presented in this deliverable is based on various sources and data types [1]. The details provided for the research community and societal stakeholders (Table 1 and 3) are grounded in analytical assumptions. Specifically, for the energy research community, more comprehensive information can be found in Deliverable D1.1.4.1, which outlines the identified requirements of researchers across different disciplines for the NFDI4Energy platform [2]. These requirements were derived from qualitative expert interviews conducted with community members (n=15).

For the group of industry stakeholders, this deliverable provides preliminary results derived from an in-person workshop conducted in November 2023 with a selected round of industry partners [3]. A description of the selected industry partners is described in D3.1.1.1, as is the description of the in-person workshop in D3.1.2.1. Detailed insights into the requirements of this stakeholder group are available in Deliverable D3.1.2.2.

As the project advances, these assumptions and preliminary findings will be refined and ultimately replaced by the final results presented in the referenced deliverables.

Related deliverables: D1.1.4.1; D3.1.1.1; D3.1.2.1; D3.1.2.2.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Figure 1 - Task Area 2 connections to other Task Areas within the NFDI4Energy consortium.

This deliverable covers the following tasks, as part of M2.1, illustrated in Fig.1:

- Identify relevant stakeholders for the NFDI4Energy platform,
- Provide overview of the incentives and barriers of platform use for three major stakeholder groups (energy research community, industry partners, societal stakeholders).

Deliverable

1. List of central stakeholder groups

Table 1 - Overview of possible chances, divided into input and output, and barriers of platform usage for the research community (colors highlight similarities to SG2 and SG3).

SG1: Research community		Possible Input	Possible Output	Barriers of platform usage
Natural sciences	- Physics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Research data - Research results (paper) - Code elements - Models and scenarios - Policy recommendations - Best practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interdisciplinary and/or transdisciplinary collaboration - Data access - Increased visibility and impact of own research - Policy influence - Real-world application of research findings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data privacy concerns - Issues regarding intellectual property and ownership - Complicated data preparation and upload procedures - Data standardization - Lack of incentives - Trust and credibility of platform - Critical user mass
	- Materials Science			
- Atmospheric Science				
- Chemistry				
- Geology				
- Environmental Science				
- Mathematics and Statistics				
- ...				
Technical sciences	- Informatics/Computer Science			
	- Engineering			
	- ...			
Social sciences and Humanities	- Sociology			
	- Political Science			
	- Economics			
	- Psychology			
	- Geography			
	- Law			
- ...				

Table 2 - Overview of possible chances, divided into input and output, and barriers of platform usage for industry partners (colors highlight similarities to SG1 and SG3).

SG2: Industry partners		Possible Input	Possible Output	Barriers of platform usage
Energy producer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Oil and Gas Companies - Solar Power Producers - Renewable Energy Companies - Hydropower Producers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy generation data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration opportunities - Data access - Real-world application of research findings 	<p>Data request:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Quality of data – Correct and appropriate data, Data preparation, different data structures, Reliability of data, Heterogeneous data sources ▪ Usability of data – Through documentation ▪ Access to data – Takes long to access open data and the need for permission, big bureaucratic hurdles in companies <p>Data provision:</p>
Energy supplier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electricity Suppliers - Natural Gas Suppliers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operational data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration opportunities - Real-world application of research findings 	
Network operators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Electricity Network Operators - Natural Gas Network Operators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grid data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration opportunities - Real-world application of research findings 	
Technology provider	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy Storage Technology Providers - Smart Grid and Energy Management Providers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy market data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration opportunities - Visibility and impact - Real-world application of research findings 	

	- Energy Efficiency and Demand Response Providers			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal issues – To ensure certain level of data privacy and security, Data protection, The need for legal assessment, Data anonymization (Automated via offline tool), Control over data Incentives to provide data – The importance of the platform that they are going to provide data for, mutually beneficial for research and industry, Research results must be made available for use
IT companies	- ICT platform provider - Cloud infrastructure provider	- ICT related operational data	- Collaboration opportunities - Data access	
Consulting	- Consulting services for energy transformation - Consulting services for energy infrastructure	- Financial and economic data	- Collaboration opportunities - Visibility and impact	

Table 3 - Overview of possible chances, divided into input and output, and barriers of platform usage for societal stakeholders (colors highlight similarities to SG1 and SG2).

SG3: Societal stakeholders		Possible Input	Possible Output	Barriers of platform usage
Public sector	- Policy- and decision makers (national, state, local level)	- Information on existing or proposed energy policies/regulations/incentives	- Platform as information basis for weighing political decisions on energy policy goals and measures	- Trust and credibility of platform

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy analysis + impact assessments - Energy transition strategies - Government funding and investment opportunities - Monitoring and reporting on the progress of energy-related initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy models and scenarios - Identification of social and technical trade-offs - Collaboration with different stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data access: Information needs to be easily understandable and readily accessible (e.g. explanations of modelling results)
	- Public Administration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aggregated energy consumption data - Data on regional renewable energy potential - Weather and climate data - Energy market data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informed decision making - Policy evaluation - Collaborative opportunities - Optimized resource allocation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of incentive: producing large amounts of data themselves - Already existing data platform: https://www.govdata.de/
Civil society	- Private households	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Energy usage data - Input on individual preferences/behavior (e.g. through survey participation) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Information on energy (transition) related topics - Energy-monitoring - Home energy audits 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Privacy concerns - Trust and credibility of platform - Data access - Relevant topics for citizens (e.g. calculation of profitability of private PV system)
	- Non-governmental organizations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grassroots feedback + community perspectives - Case study results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaboration opportunities - Access to research and modelling results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trust and credibility of platform

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Best practices - Policy recommendations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data on energy policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Missing network opportunities - Data access
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Community energy initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Real-world-data - Knowledge about community engagement strategies and financing models - Information on social and environmental benefits and challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge exchange - Collaboration opportunities - Scaling opportunities - Policy insights 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Trust and credibility of platform - Privacy concerns - Data access

2. Graphical stakeholder overview

Figure 2 - Overview of different stakeholder types.

3. Potential stakeholder involvement

Figure 3 - Involvement of stakeholder groups in data lifecycle.

Figure 4 - Involvement of stakeholder groups in key services of the NFDI4Energy platform.

References

- [1] C. Speck, P. Jaquart, C. Weinhardt, J. Lilliestam, M. Schäfer, A. Weidlich, J. Zilles, and N. Kerker, "Transparency and involvement of society and policy in a data sharing platform," in Proc. 1st Conf. Res. Data Infrastruct. (CoRDI), 2023. doi: <https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.327>
- [2] F. M. Hoffart, N. Kerker, and O. Werth, "An energy data service platform for whom? Understanding the needs of the energy research community," in NFDI4Energy Conf. 2024, Hanover, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10778102>
- [3] C. Speck, S. Herrmann, Z. Pan, F. Sedighi, C. Seiwerth, M. Niebisch, and C. Weinhardt, "Drivers and challenges of open data from an energy industry perspective," in Proc. 1st NFDI4Energy Conf., Hanover, Germany, Feb. 14, 2024. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10658531>